

INTELLECTUAL ACTIVITY OF THE PEDAGOGUE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ANALYTICAL THINKING AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: In the article, the intellectual activity of the pedagogue in the development of analytical thinking and its specific characteristics, types of intelligence are studied and analyzed.

Key words: analytical thinking, structural structure, logical, critical and analytical thinking, intellectual activity, intelligence.

INTRODUCTION

In order to justify the necessity of developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues, it is appropriate to consider the content and essence of the concept of analytical thinking and its expression in dictionaries. It is also important to consider socio-philosophical and pedagogical aspects of analytical thinking.

As a result of the development of science, it is known that the mental-intellectual phenomenon called thinking is not one-sided. For example, thinking is different from independent thinking, and analytical thinking is different from all other forms of thinking [3]. Analytical thinking is one of the forms of thinking that stands out for its effectiveness in increasing a person's erudition and intelligence. Because analytical thinking requires approaching the studied object from different sides, comprehensively checking its internal and external relations and coming to a stop. Since ancient times, the owners of such thinking were especially valued. People who could think like this were called analysts in ancient Greece. Since then, a unique complex type of thinking has been called analytics.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Analytical thinking has been researched by many scientists in various disciplines, especially philosophy, psychology and pedagogy, and this process continues today. Among them, D. Sharipova, O. Musurmonova, M. Kuronov, U. Mahkamov, R. Safarova, Sh. Mardonov, D. Roziyeva, N. Egamberdiyeva, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Sharipov, O. Jamoldinova, V. Slastenin, I. Isayev, Y. Shiyanov, Z. T. Soliyeva's scientific research studies have explored the philosophical, psychological and pedagogical aspects of analytical thinking, existing problems and the factors to overcome them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The process of developing analytical thinking is related to the development of intellectual activity of future pedagogues. Intellectual skills include the development of memory; development of perception; the development of imagination; reflects the development of attention [5].

Intellect is a personality trait, the ability to clearly and deeply reflect objects and events of objective existence in our mind with their specific connections and laws.

Intelligence is seen in all mental processes, primarily in thinking and creative imagination. It is more often observed when solving a bright new problem independently.

Due to the fact that intelligence is developed at different levels in different people, there are several qualities:

intelligibility of the mind - the simplicity and reliability of thoughts, the absence of some kind of thought. This is not only intellectual, but in some sense moral. For the intelligibility of the mind is usually to feel responsible not only for action, but also for thoughts;

rationality of the mind is a strict continuity and systematicity in thinking;

depth of mind or thoughtfulness - the ability to recognize uniqueness in objects and events;

breadth of mind - the ability to think taking into account all aspects of the issue;

softness and flexibility of mind - absence of stereotypes, ability to change thinking;

independence and originality. It is not a mere softness of mind, but innovation is a creative feature of mental activity;

the criticality of the mind is the absence of unexamined, simply received judgments, the existence of a deeply studied, analyzed, serious attitude to denials. All these individual characteristics of the human mind appear in the process of work, it is formed and developed [2].

According to psychologist G. Gardner, every person has at least VIII type of intelligence:

I. A person with verbal-linguistic intelligence likes to read, learns words easily, has a large vocabulary, likes to create. Such intelligence is strongly developed in poets, writers and speakers.

II. Logical-mathematical intelligence is characteristic of individuals who like to calculate and work with numbers, solve logical problems and puzzles, like to play chess, think more abstractly than their peers, understand cause and effect relationships.

III. A person with visual-spatial intelligence thinks with visible images, reads maps, drawings, diagrams more easily than text, likes to indulge in fantasies and engage in art, draws well, has interesting three o works on the construction of dimensional models, receives more information from illustrations than from words during reading. This type of intelligence is related to visual imagination, the sense of mastery, and the ability to remember objects by sight, and includes the ability to create internal mental images.

IV. The type of motor-motor intelligence shows high sports results; imitates the gestures, facial expressions, actions of others well; likes to take things apart and put them back together; he touches everything he sees with his hands; likes to run, jump, wrestle, shows that he has talent for crafts.

V. This type of musical-rhythmic intelligence is based on knowledge and perception of rhythm, including musical images and sounds around us. This type is more developed in composers, musicians, singers and players.

VI. Interpersonal intelligence likes to connect with peers, takes the lead in situations, likes to play with and teach other children, can grieve together, other children seek to be around him.

VII. A self-directed intellectual exhibits a sense of independence and willpower, truly recognizes his strengths and weaknesses, performs tasks well when nothing interferes with him, is self-contained, and alone. prefers to work on the trail, clearly describes his feelings, learns from his mistakes, knows his worth.

VIII. Nature-oriented intelligence shows interest in natural phenomena, animals, and plants, demonstrates the ability to understand the natural world, distinguish signs and characteristics of the surrounding environment, and classify them.

The German philosopher Immanuel Kant called analytics a human ability to understand, and in his work "Critique of Pure Consciousness" he was the first to suggest dividing the way of knowing into two stages, such as analytical and synthetic thinking. He claims that analytical thinking is a priori, that is, it does not need confirmation in experience. Therefore, he writes: "analytical thinking helps to understand the existing knowledge more vividly."

Researcher Sh. According to Hasanov, "analytical thinking is the art of analytical thinking, the ability to come to a comprehensive, clear, deep, deep, meaningful, solid conclusion about a problem, issue, information, event, in the process of studying it. A person with an analytical mindset carefully studies the object under analysis in every way: divides complex information into parts, thinks seriously about every word, sentence, detail, thing, logically connects the parts, comes to an acceptable conclusion and makes the necessary decisions. does. When thinking about any phenomenon, the possessor of analytical ability does not limit himself to reading the outer meaning of the event, but also tries to determine its inner layers. As a result, a comprehensive understanding of the analyzed object is created. Analytical thinking serves to ensure that a problem or issue is solved easily and quickly, correctly and precisely" [4]. Based on this tariff, the researcher justifies the manifestation of analytical thinking as follows: "analytical thinking is a type of mental activity strictly connected with logic, aimed at clear, correct, objective, comprehensive analysis of the subject; Analytical thinking is a productive way of thinking that allows analyzing, reacting, understanding the past, understanding the present, predicting the future, defining promising ways of development in all spheres of social life; analytical thinking is a creative way of thinking that encourages a person to promote innovative ideas, create new technologies, and implement them; development of analytical thinking ability of students in the educational system allows to raise a well-rounded generation that thinks independently, can quickly find a rational solution to any problem, and is far from intellectual dependence. Analytical thinking is a generator of intelligence that gives a person the ability to perceive people and the world, rationally activates his thinking mechanism" [4]. So, analytical thinking is the type of thinking that stands out for its effectiveness in increasing the erudition and intelligence of a person. Because analytical thinking requires approaching the studied object from different sides, comprehensively checking its internal and external relations and coming to a stop. Aspects such as speed of thinking, ability to approach the problem from different sides, comprehensiveness, and finding the most suitable and effective solution to the problem are prioritized in analytical thinking. Since ancient times, the owners of such thinking were especially valued. People who could think like this were called analysts in ancient Greece. Since then, a unique complex type of thinking has been called analytics.

CONCLUSION. In general, there are different ways of thinking, and each of them tries to replace the universal way of thinking that can reveal the truth. However, "many of them were rejected to a certain extent because they could not meet the requirements of the new era in the process of historical development. Sophistic, eclectic, metaphysical, mechanistic, metaphysical and other ways of thinking are among them. Although they are still used spontaneously today, they cannot be the dominant method of modern thinking. Similarly, dialectical and synergetic methods that attract the attention of many people today are unlikely to remain the absolute, only way of human thinking. They also occupy a special place among other important methods in the "pillapoya" of universal thinking" [1]. Humanity has

learned to use each of these methods in the right field and when necessary, and in practice it continues to operate based on this experience.

In conclusion, thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social events, and reality, as well as the main condition for the implementation of human activity, while analytical thinking is the art of analytical thinking, analyzing a problem, issue, information, event. in the process of learning, the ability to come to a comprehensive, accurate, deep, deep, meaningful, and solid conclusion about it is revealed.

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